

Phytochemical Analysis and Antioxidant Evaluation of Scent Leaf (*Ocimum Gratissimum*)

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Abstract— *Ocimum gratissimum* (commonly known as Scent leaf) is a widely utilized herb in traditional African medicine, reputed for its therapeutic properties, especially in treating microbial infections, oxidative stress-related disorders, and gastrointestinal disturbances. This study aimed to assess both the qualitative and quantitative phytochemical constituents as well as the antioxidant activity of aqueous extracts of *Ocimum gratissimum* leaves. The qualitative phytochemical screening revealed the presence of bioactive constituents such as saponins, tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, and steroids. Quantitative analysis showed high concentrations of tannins (6.80 mg/g), alkaloids (4.66 mg/g), and saponins (2.40 mg/g), indicating that the plant possesses potent pharmacologically active compounds. The antioxidant potential of the extract, as measured by the DPPH radical scavenging assay, demonstrated a dose-dependent activity with the maximum scavenging effect of 83.9% at 100 µg/ml concentration. These results strongly support the traditional use of *O. gratissimum* in managing diseases associated with oxidative stress and support its further investigation for pharmaceutical applications.

Keywords- *Ocimum gratissimum*, scent leaf, Traditional system of medicine, pharmaceutical application, Antioxidant, Phytochemical.

I. INTRODUCTION

Plants have been identified and known throughout human history to have medicinal properties such as their roots, stems, leaves and seeds possess therapeutic, tonic, and other pharmacological potentials. They are used as drug, food additives and for their nutritive values. Medicinal values of some plants lie in the chemical substances that produce definite physiological actions in their body. Among the chemical substances are phytochemicals which are bioactive natural compounds found in plants. Kolawole et al, (2018). Many plants that are used in traditional medicine to alleviate symptoms of illnesses have been found to possess phytochemicals, examples of such plants include; *Azadirachta indica* (Dogonyaro), *Vernonia amygdalina* (Bitter leaf), *Allium sativum* (Garlic), *Zingiber officinale* (Ginger), *Moringa oleifera* (Moringa), *Ocimum gratissimum* (Scent leaf) etc. Chemical compounds present in these plants mediate their effects on human body through processes identical to those already well understood from chemical compounds in conventional drugs.

This herbal medications do not differ greatly from conventional drugs in terms of their effects on the body. This enables herbal medicines to be effective as well as having the potentials to cause harmful side effects (Tapsil et al., 2006). The use of herbs and search for drugs and dietary supplements derived from plants have accelerated in recent years because medicinal plants are known to contain some chemical substances which can be used for treatment purposes or to produce drugs (Sofowora, 1999). Medicinal plants play vital roles in the health of individuals, in fact most modern drugs are derived from them (WHO, 2004). Medicinal plant based drugs have the advantage of being simple, effective and have broad spectrum activity. An ethno-botanical and ubiquitous plant serve as rich resources of natural drugs for research development. With the crises of covid-19 pandemic, researchers throughout the world are combing the earth searching for vaccines, remedies and possible breakthrough with the use of conventional drugs and

medicinal plants. Knowledge of the chemical constituents of plants is necessary for the discovery of the therapeutic agents in plants.

Ocimum gratissimum L. commonly called scent leaf originated from Africa and southern Asia. It is a perennial scrub belonging to the family Lamiaceae. It grows up to 1-3m high, the stem which bears the leaves are dark brown. *O. Gratissimum* leaves are opposite to each other, narrow and oval in shape and they (leaves) grow to about 5-13cm in length and 3-9cm in width. *Ocimum gratissimum* has been used extensively in the traditional system of medicine in many countries. In the Northeast of Brazil, it is used for medicinal, condiment and culinary purpose. The flowers and the leaves of this plant are rich in essential oils which makes it an excellent recipe in the preparation of teas and infusion (Rabelo et al., 2003). Brazilian tropical forest inhabitants use a decoction of *Ocimum gratissimum* roots as a sedative for children (Freire et al., 2006).

People of Kenyan and sub-Saharan African communities' use *Ocimum gratissimum* for various purposes like, the leaves are rubbed between the palms and sniffed as a treatment for blocked nostrils, they are also used for abdominal pains, sore eyes, ear infections, coughs, fever, convulsions, tooth ache and regulation of menstruation (Matasyoh et al., 2007). In India, the whole plant has been used for the treatment of sunstroke, headache, influenza, as a diaphoretic, antipyretic and for its anti-inflammatory activity (Prajapati et al., 2003). In the coastal areas of Nigeria, the plant is used in the treatment of epilepsy, high fever and diarrhea (Effraim et al., 2003). In the Savannah areas, decoctions of the leaves are used to treat mental illness (Akinmoladun et al., 2007). *Ocimum gratissimum* is used by the Ibos of South eastern Nigeria in the management of the baby's cord, to keep the wound surfaces sterile. It is also used in the treatment of fungal infections, fever, cold and catarrh (Ijeh et al., 2005). There are many tribes in Nigeria that use the leaves extract in the treatment of diarrhea, while the cold leaves

infusion is used for relief of stomach upset and hemorrhoids (Kabir et al., 2005). The plant is commonly used in folk medicine to treat different diseases such as upper respiratory tract infections, diarrhea, headache, diseases of the eye, skin diseases, pneumonia, cough, fever and conjunctivitis (Adebolu et al., 2005). *Ocimum gratissimum* in the coastal areas of Nigeria is used in the treatment of epilepsy (Osifor, 1992), high fever (Oliver, 1980) and diarrhea (Oliver, 1980; Sofowora, 1999). The whole plant is used as an antinutritional agent throughout West Africa (Iwu et al., 1999). The study is aimed at investigating the phytochemical screening and proximate composition of ethanol leave extracts of *Ocimum gratissimum*.

Many research in food and pharmaceuticals is focused on the use of materials as close to nature as possible to limit exposure to harmful synthetic substances. Alternatives are being sought for popular plant-based materials leading to increased attention to underutilized plants and creating ripple effects in agriculture, agribusiness, health and pharmaceuticals. A plant that has attained prominence in Nigeria and in the rain forests of West Africa is the *Ocimum gratissimum*. The plant is best known for the juicy pulp of its fruit but the traditional therapeutic use of parts of the plants are also common. Some authors have investigated and documented some benefits obtained from its leaves, stem, root and fruits. This work focuses on the phytochemical analysis and antioxidant activities of *Ocimum gratissimum*.

Antioxidants play a crucial role in combating oxidative stress, a factor implicated in numerous chronic diseases. Scent leaf has been a cornerstone of Ayurvedic medicine for millennia. This research aims to bridge the gap between traditional wisdom and modern scientific understanding, providing empirical evidence for its long-standing use in healthcare practices. Scientific validation of Tulsi's beneficial properties may promote its cultivation, contributing to biodiversity conservation and offering sustainable agricultural opportunities for farmers. While preliminary studies have indicated the presence of antioxidants in scent leaf, a thorough, systematic evaluation is essential to fully characterize its antioxidant profile. This study will provide a detailed analysis of the types, concentrations, and efficacy of antioxidants present in scent leaves.

The Study aims to evaluate the phytochemical analysis and *in vitro* antioxidant analysis of Scent leaves (*Ocimum gratissimum*).

Description of Scent (*Ocimum gratissimum*) Leaf

The use of plant materials as spices, condiments and for medicinal purposes dates back to the history of mankind (Nweze et al.:2000). Recently, the exploitation of wild plants for medicinal purposes has gained more acceptances in many countries of the world. To further underscore the importance of herbal medicine, most national governments have established the traditional medicine regulatory council under the supervision of their various health ministries to tap the numerous potentials of herbs. This may be because traditional medicine has long been practiced even before the orthodox medical practice appeared. *Ocimum gratissimum* belongs to the group of plants known as spices. The plant is an erect small plumb with many barnacles usually not more than 1 m high (Vierra and Simon, 2000). It is of the family Labiatea, genus *Ocimum* and species *gratissimum*. In South East Asia, it is cultivated as a home garden crop but it is grown on a commercial scale in Vietnam. In Nigeria, it is Efinrinin Yoruba, Diadoyal in Hausa and Nchuanwu in Igbo (Owulade,

2004). It is used for a variety of reasons. In culinary, it is used in salads, soups, pastas, vinegars and jellies in many parts of the world. The Thai people are popularly known to use it in food flavoring. In traditional medicine, the leaves have been used as a general tonic and anti-diarrhea agent and for the treatment of conjunctivitis by instilling directly into the eyes; the leaf oil when mixed with alcohol is applied as a lotion for skin infections, and taken internally for bronchitis. The dried leaves are snuffed to alleviate headaches and fever among other uses (Iwu, 1993). Although, conventional antibiotics have been very useful in orthodox medicine, it has been argued by many that its concomitant use with herbal extracts is not desirable as one normally antagonizes the activity of the other. Considering the fact that *Ocimum gratissimum* is used in most local dishes/foods to achieve a variety of purposes, there is need to ascertain if its extract antagonizes or acts as a synergy when used together with conventional antibiotics. In addition, despite the fact that the various extracts of *Ocimum. gratissimum* have been tested *in vitro* and shown to be active against some bacterial and fungal isolates (Silva et al, 2005).

Fig. 1: Image of *Ocimum. Gratissimum*

Source: Wikipedia.org

Nomenclature and Taxonomy of *Ocimum gratissimum*

Kingdom: Plantae –Plants

Subkingdom: Tracheobionta – Vascular plants

Superdivision: Spermatophyta– Seed plants

Division: Magnoliophyta–Flowering plants

Class: Magnoliopsida– Dicotyledons

Subclass: Asteridae

Order: Lamiales

Family: Lamiaceae– Mint family

Genus: *Ocimum*L. – basil

Species: *gratissimum* L. African basil

A. MEDICINAL USES OF *OCIMUM GRATISSIMUM*

Ocimum gratissimum has been used extensively in the traditional system of medicine in many countries. In the North East of Brazil, it is used for medicinal, condiments and culinary purpose. The flowers and the leaves of this plant are rich in essential oil, so it is used in the preparation of teas and infusion

(Rabelo et al, 2003). In the Coastal areas of Nigeria, the plant is used in the treatment of epilepsy, high fever and diarrhea. In the Savannah areas, decoctions of the leaves are to treat mental illness (Akinmoladun et al., 2007). *Ocimum gratissimum* is used by the Ibos of the South Eastern Nigeria in the management of the baby's cord, to keep the wound surfaces sterile. It is also used in the treatment of fungal infections, cold and catarrh (Ijeh et al., 2005). Brazilian tropical forest inhabitants used a decoction of *Ocimum. gratissimum* roots as a sedative for children. People of Kenya and Sub-Sahara Africa used it in the treatment of abdominal pains, sore eyes, infections, coughs, barrenness, fever, convulsions and tooth gargle, regulation of menstruation and as a cure for the prolapsed of the rectum. In India, the whole plant has been used for the treatment of sunstroke, headache and influenza, as a diaphoretic, antipyretic and for its anti-inflammatory activities (Tania et al., 2006).

The tribes of Nigeria use the leaves extract in the treatment of diarrhea, while the cold leave infusions are used for the relief of stomach upset and haemorrhoids (Kabir et al, 2005). The plant is commonly used in folk medicine to treat different diseases such as upper respiratory tract infection, diarrhea, headache, disease of the eye, skin diseases, pneumonia, cough, fever and conjunctivitis (Adebolu and Salau, 2005). The infusion of *Ocimum. gratissimum* leaves is used as pulmonary antisepticum, antitussivum antispasmodic (Ngassoum et al,2003).

B. ALTERNATIVE AND COMPLIMENTARY MEDICINAL USES

1) Wound Healing

Persistent microvascular hyperpermeability to plasma proteins is a characteristic feature of normal wound healing. Evan's blue dye (200mg/kg body weight) in normal saline was administered intravenously through marginal ear vein of experimental rabbits (n=5). Each animal served as its own control. One hour after evan's blue administration, 0.1ml each of *Ocimum gratissimum* oil, histamine dihydrochloride (30µ g/ml) and normal saline were randomly administered by intra- dermal injection at the prepared sites on each of the animals. Increase in vascular permeability was assessed by dye effusion test. Analysis of the differences in vascular permeability between treatment groups showed that *Ocimum gratissimum* oil in intensity and duration was significantly ($p < 0.05$) more effective in increasing cutaneous capillary permeability over a 24h period after treatment. The ability of *Ocimum gratissimum* oil in increasing vascular permeability may be one of the factors that contribute to its wound healing property (Orafidiya et al, 2005).

2) Anti-Inflammatory

The following study reports the inhibitory effect produced by chemical constituents of essential oils of three plants used in traditional medicine as anti-inflammatory and analgesic drugs, in vitro, on soybean lipoyxygenase L-1 and cyclooxygenase function of prostaglandin H synthase (PGHS), the two enzymes involved in the production of mediators of inflammation. The essential oils were extracted from plants *Ocimum gratissimum* along with two other oils, *Ocimum gratissimum* inhibited the two enzymes, cyclooxygenase function of PGHS and lipoyxygenase L-1, with an IC₅₀= 125g/ml and 144g/ml (Sahouo et al, 2003).

3) Analgesic Activity

The pharmacological activities of aqueous extracts of *Ocimum gratissimum* was screened for isolated rabbit jejunum (IRJ); rat stomach strip (RSS); and analgesic properties in mice. The extract caused a dose-dependent inhibition of the rabbit jejunum spontaneous pendular movement. The blocking effect on acetylcholine induced contraction was non- competitive in the rat stomach strip since maximum contractions were suppressed and no parallel shift was observed in the curve. The result of the analgesic study showed that the extract evoked a prolongation of reaction time of 85% over 20min observation time of 85% over 20min observation time with no overt signs of toxicity. The results suggest the presence of analgesic and spasmolytic activities (Aziba et al,1999).

Health Benefits of *Ocimum gratissimum* leaves

The plant has numerous medical benefits. Its leaves are a nerve tonic, improve memory, and aid in clearing mucus and catarrh from the bronchial tubes. The leaves encourage sweating and strengthen the stomach. Colds and mucilaginous fever are the plant's seeds. Many fevers can only be treated with basil leaves. Tender leaves that have been boiled with tea can be used as a preventative measure against diseases like malaria and dengue fever during the rainy seasons. A decoction of the leaves cooked in half water with powdered cardamom and combined with sugar and milk lowers the temperature in cases of cute fevers.

Types of Reactive Species

Reactive oxygen Species (ROS)	Reactive nitrogen species (RNS)
Superoxide: O_2^-	Nitric acid NO-
Hydroxyl: OH-Alkoxy: RO-	Nitrous acid: NHO_2
Hydrogen peroxide: H_2O_2	Nitrogen dioxide: NO_2
Ozone: O_3	Perioxynitrite: $ONOO$
Singlet oxygen: Δg	Perioxynitrous acid: $ONOOH$

Source: Caimi et al., (2004)

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. MATERIALS/REAGENTS

Materials include; Beakers, conical flasks, bottles, test tubes thermometer and pipettes, Water, and ethanol.

B. SAMPLE COLLECTION

Scent leaves (*Ocimum gratissimum*) sample was purchased from Nasarawa Market in Nasarawa local Government area, Nasarawa State Nigeria. The identification and authentication of the samples were done in department of biological science.

C. AQUEOUS EXTRACT PREPARATION

About 120g of the powdered sample was extracted with solvent combination (via maceration) of distilled water for 48hrs using the maceration method described by Malairjan et al. (2008). One litre of distilled water was used. The mixtures was decanted and filtered using sterile whatman paper No1.

The filtrate was measured up to 600ml and evaporated to dryness using a freeze dryer to obtain a 9.92 % yield.

D. PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

The plant extracts was further used for chemical tests for the presence of following phytochemicals such as, alkaloids, saponin, tannin, flavonoids, steroids and terpenoids using the methods mentioned below:-

1) Test for Saponins

About 5.0ml aliquot of the extract was diluted with 20ml of deionized water, shaken vigorously and observed. Persistent foaming indicated the presence of saponins.

2) Test for Alkaloids

A known quantity of the extract, 0.1g was added to 6ml of dilute hydrochloric acid and boiled, after boiling, it was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was divided into three aliquot and subjected to the following tests. To the first portion, 2 drops of Dragendorff's reagent was added. The formation of a red precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids. To the second portion, 2 drops of Meyer's reagent was added. A creamy white precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids. To the third portion, 2 drops of Wagner's reagent was added. A reddish-brown precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids.

3) Test for Tannins

The extract, 1 ml was added to 10 ml of deionised water and then treated with 3 drops of ferric chloride. A greenish-brown precipitate was observed which indicate the presence of tannins.

4) Test for Flavonoides

A quantity of the extract was boiled in ethylacetate (10 ml) for 3 minutes, filtered and cooled. Then the filtrate (4 ml) was shaken with 1ml of dilute ammonia solution. An intense yellow colouration was observed which indicate the presence of flavonoids.

5) Test for Terpenoids

Nine millilitre (9 ml) of ethanol was added to 1g of the extract and refluxed for a few minutes and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated down to 2.5 ml in a boiling water bath. Hot distilled water (5ml) was added to the concentrated solution; the mixture was allowed to stand for 1 hour and the waxy mater was filtered off. The filtrate was extracted with 2.5 ml of chloroform using a separating funnel. The chloroform extract was evaporated to dryness in a water bath and dissolved in 3 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid and then heated for 10 min in a water bath. A grey colour was observed which indicate the presence of terpenoids.

6) Test for Steroids

A known quantity of the test sample was extracted in the chloroform and filtered. The filtrate was mixed with 2 ml of conc. H₂SO₄ carefully so that the sulphuric acid formed a lower layer. A reddish-brown colour at the was observed which indicate the presence of steroidal ring.

E. QUANTITATIVE PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF SCENT LEAVES (OCIMUM GRATISSIMUM) EXTRACT

The leave extracts were quantitatively determined according to the method of Harborne (1973) and Trease and Evans (2002).

1) Quantitative Estimation of Alkaloids

To 1ml of test extract 5 ml pH 4.7 phosphate Buffer was added and 5 ml BCG solution and shake a mixture with 4 ml of chloroform. The extracts were collected in a 10-ml volumetric flask and then diluted to adjust volume with chloroform. The absorbance of the complex in chloroform was measured at 470 nm against blank prepared as above but without extract. Atropine is used as a standard material and compared the assay with Atropine equivalents.

2) Quantitative Estimation of flavanoids

Total flavonoid content was determined by Aluminium chloride method using catechin as a standard. 1ml of test sample and 4 ml of water was added to a volumetric flask (10 ml volume). After 5 min 0.3 ml of 5 % Sodium nitrite, 0.3 ml of 10% Aluminium chloride was added. After 6 min incubation at room temperature, 2 ml of 1 M Sodium hydroxide was added to the reaction mixture. Immediately the final volume was made up to 10 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured at 510 nm against a blank spectrophotometrically. Results were expressed as catechin equivalents (mg catechin/g dried extract).

3) Quantitative Estimation of Saponins

Test extract was dissolved in 80% methanol, 2ml of Vanilin in ethanol was added, mixed well and the 2ml of 72% sulphuric acid solution was added, mixed well and heated on a water bath at 600 c for 10min, absorbance was measured at 544nm against reagent blank. Diosgenin is used as a standard material and compared the assay with Diosgenin equivalents.

4) Quantitative Estimation of Steroids

1ml of test extract of steroid solution was transferred into 10 ml volumetric flasks. Sulphuric acid (4N, 2ml) and iron (III) chloride (0.5% w/v, 2 ml), was added, followed by potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) solution (0.5% w/v, 0.5 ml). The mixture was heated in a water-bath maintained at 70±20 C for 30 minutes with occasional shaking and diluted to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 780 nm against the reagent blank.

5) Quantitative Estimation of Terpenoids

Nine millilitre (9 ml) of ethanol was added to 1g of the extract and refluxed for a few minutes and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated down to 2.5 ml in a boiling water bath. Hot distilled water (5ml) was added to the concentrated solution; the mixture was allowed to stand for 1 hour and the waxy mater was filtered off. The filtrate was extracted with 2.5 ml of chloroform using a separating funnel. The chloroform extract was evaporated to dryness in a water bath and dissolved in 3 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid and then heated for 10 min in a water bath. A grey colour was observed which indicate the presence of terpenoids.

F. DETERMINATION OF IN VITRO ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITIES OF THE STUDIED PLANT EXTRACTS

Determination of 2,2, Diphenyl-1-Picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) Radical Scavenging Activities.

The DPPH radical scavenging assay was performed using 2,2 diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) according to the method described by Brand-Williams et al. (1995) with some modifications. five different concentrations of the *Ocimum gratissimum* plant extracts (0.0625, 0.125, 0.25, 0.5, and 1 mg/ml) were prepared in methanol (analytical grade). The same concentrations were also prepared for L-ascorbic acid, which was used as a standard antioxidant. 1 ml of each studied extract was transferred into a clean test tube into which 0.5 ml of 0.3 m MDPPH in methanol was added. and mixture was shaken and left to stand in the dark at room temperature for 15 minutes.

Blank solutions comprising of the studied extract solutions (2.5 ml) and 1 ml of methanol were used as base line. The negative control comprised 2.5 ml of DPPH solution and 1 ml of methanol, while L-ascorbic acid at the same concentrations as the studied extracts were used as the positive control. After incubation in the dark, the absorbance values were measured at 517 nm using a spectrophotometer. and experiments were performed in triplicate. The DPPH radical scavenging activity was estimated using the equation described by Brand-Williams et al. (1995).

$$\% \text{ Radical scavenging activity} = \left(\frac{A_c - A_s}{A_c} \times 100 \right)$$

Where A_s is the absorbance of the sample and A_c is the absorbance of the control.

The half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of the extracts was computed from a plot of percentage DPPH free radical inhibition versus the extract concentration.

III. RESULTS

Table 1: Qualitative phytochemical constituents present in aqueous extract of Scent leaves (*Ocimum gratissimum*).

Phytochemicals	Aqueous extract
Saponin	+
Tanin	+
Flavonoid	+
Alkaloids	+
Terpenoids	+
Steroids	+

Key: (+) = Represent present, (-) = Represent absent

Table 2: Quantitative phytochemical constituents present in aqueous extract of Scent leaves (*Ocimum gratissimum*).

Phytochemicals	Concentration (mg/g)
Steroids	0.91
Alkaloids	4.66
Flavonoid	1.98
Tannin	6.80
Saponin	2.40
Terpenoids	1.38

Table 3: Results on the(I) DPPH radical scavenging activities of Scent leaves (*Ocimum gratissimum*)

Concentration(ug/ml)	Absorbance of sample	%DPPH Scavenging activity
20	0.725	27.5
40	0.559	44.1
60	0.396	60.4
80	0.255	74.5
100	0.161	83.9

Fig.2: Graph representing the inhibitory concentration at IC 50 which was (48ug/ml)

IV. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Phytochemicals are secondary metabolites synthesized by plants for defense and are known to contribute to their medicinal properties. Table 1 shows the presence of six major phytochemical groups: alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, terpenoids, and steroids. These bioactive compounds are widely known for their health benefits, Alkaloids, found in considerable amounts (4.66 mg/g), are associated with analgesic, antimalarial, and antimicrobial effects (Sasidharan et al., 2011). Alkaloids also play a role in inhibiting cancer cell proliferation (Cushnie et al., 2014). Flavonoids (1.98 mg/g) are potent antioxidants known to prevent oxidative damage to

cells by neutralizing free radicals. They also exhibit anti-inflammatory, anti-carcinogenic, and cardio-protective effects (Pietta, 2000). Tannins had the highest concentration (6.80 mg/g), supporting their relevance in antimicrobial activity, wound healing, and anti-diarrheal properties (Haslam, 1996). Saponins (2.40 mg/g) are implicated in cholesterol-lowering, immunostimulatory, and anti-cancer activities (Man et al., 2010). Terpenoids (1.38 mg/g) and steroids (0.91 mg/g) contribute to anti-inflammatory, antiviral, and hormonal balancing effects (Rabi & Bishayee, 2009).

Table 3 presents data on the DPPH radical scavenging activity of the aqueous extract of *O. gratissimum*. DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) is a stable free radical commonly used to evaluate antioxidant capacity. The study showed a clear dose-dependent relationship: At 20 µg/ml, scavenging activity was 27.5%. At 100 µg/ml, the activity rose to 83.9%. The IC₅₀ value, representing the concentration required to scavenge 50% of the DPPH radicals, was calculated as 48 µg/mL. A lower IC₅₀ value denotes higher antioxidant efficiency. Compared to other commonly consumed herbs and vegetables, *Ocimum gratissimum* falls within the range of potent natural antioxidants. Previous studies have similarly reported strong antioxidant properties of *Ocimum gratissimum*, attributing these to its high content of eugenol, thymol, flavonoids, and phenolic acids (Okoli et al., 2010). This increase confirms that the extract possesses strong radical scavenging potential. A DPPH scavenging value above 70% is considered significantly high and indicative of potent antioxidant activity (Brand-Williams et al., 1995). The high antioxidant potential of the extract is most likely due to the synergistic effects of flavonoids, tannins, and saponins. Flavonoids, for example, are excellent electron donors and can reduce lipid peroxidation and DNA damage. Tannins and phenolic compounds stabilize ROS through hydrogen donation, further enhancing the extract's antioxidant efficacy (Rice-Evans et al., 1997). Comparative studies by Ebrahimzadeh et al. (2009) and Ijeh et al. (2005) have demonstrated similar antioxidant trends in *Ocimum* species, thus supporting the current findings.

B. CONCLUSION

The results of this study reveal that the aqueous extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* is a rich source of biologically active phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, terpenoids, and steroids. Quantitative analysis showed tannins and alkaloids to be the most abundant, which contributes significantly to its antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant effects. Furthermore, the extract exhibited a strong dose-dependent antioxidant activity, achieving 83.9% DPPH radical inhibition at 100 µg/ml. This suggests that the plant has promising therapeutic potential against oxidative stress-induced cellular damage and associated chronic diseases. These findings support the traditional use of Scent leaf as a functional food and medicinal plant. Given the growing interest in plant-based therapeutics, *Ocimum gratissimum* stands out as a valuable source for natural antioxidant and pharmaceutical product development. However, despite its promising properties, further in-depth studies are needed to fully exploit its pharmacological

benefits, optimize its dosage, and evaluate its safety for clinical applications.

C. RECOMMENDATIONS

The bioactive constituents responsible for the antioxidant activity should be isolated and structurally characterized using techniques such as HPLC, GC-MS, and FTIR for precise identification. Acute and chronic toxicity studies should be conducted to establish the safety profile of the aqueous extract, especially for long-term human consumption. The in vitro antioxidant potential observed in this study should be confirmed using in vivo models of oxidative stress to validate therapeutic relevance. Given its bioactive potential, the extract should be explored for development into nutraceuticals, herbal teas, dietary supplements, and skincare products. Other *Ocimum* species should be studied in parallel for their phytochemical and antioxidant profiles to identify superior varieties for industrial use. Given its medicinal value, there should be advocacy for the wider cultivation of *O. gratissimum*, especially in rural communities, as a low-cost, natural health resource.

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